

Factors influencing post BCG vaccination scar formation amongst vaccinated children: a case study of a tertiary institution in Northeastern Nigeria.

Solomon G Bulus,^{1*} Olutayo F Martins,² Wasinda S Bulus,¹ Hayatu Ahmad.¹

¹ Department of Paediatrics, Modibbo Adama University Teaching Hospital, Yola, Adamawa, Nigeria.

² Department of Public Health, Modibbo Adama University Teaching Hospital, Yola, Adamawa, Nigeria

Corresponding author: *Dr. Solomon G. Bulus Department of Paediatrics, Modibbo Adama University Teaching Hospital, Yola, Adamawa, Nigeria. Tel: No: +2348036516103. Email: solbulus@yahoo.com

Abstract

Introduction: Bacille Calmette-Guerin (BCG) vaccination against tuberculosis has been shown to reduce TB incidence and improve child survival. The presence of a BCG scar following vaccination indicates an appropriate immune response and may be associated with lower child mortality. This study aims to assess the factors associated with BCG scarring in vaccinated children in Yola, Northeastern Nigeria. **Materials and Methods:** The study was descriptive and cross-sectional. Children were selected and physically examined for a BCG scar. Data were analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences software (SPSS). Chi-square test was used for the association between categorical variables. $P < 0.05$ was considered significant. **Results:** A total of 277 children were enrolled, 146(52.7%) were males and 131(47.3%) females, giving a male: female ratio of 1.1:1. The median age was 6 months and 160(57.8%) were aged less than six months. Of the 277 children, 259 had the BCG scar, giving a prevalence of 93.5%, and 18 were without a scar, giving a BCG scar failure prevalence of 6.5%. Of the factors related to BCG scars, only children on drugs (medications like antibiotics or analgesics) during administration of BCG vaccines were found to be statistically significant to BCG scarring (p value = 0.013). **Conclusion:** The study demonstrated a high prevalence of BCG scars, and administering the BCG vaccine while children are on medications (analgesics or antibiotics) was significantly associated with BCG scar formation. We therefore recommend further studies to understand the observed association.

Keywords: BCG, Scar, Vaccination

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Introduction

Bacille Calmette-Guérin (BCG) is one of the most widely used vaccines globally. It is a live-attenuated *Mycobacterium bovis* vaccine that protects against severe forms of tuberculosis (TB) and other mycobacterial diseases.¹ In 2024, over 10 million people contracted TB globally, with over one million deaths resulting from the disease. Nigeria has the highest burden of TB in Africa, and is among the eight countries harbouring two-thirds of global TB cases.² The World Health Organization advocates the use of Bacille Calmette-Guerin vaccine for vaccinating newborns at birth or first contact with health services, especially in developing countries or settings with a high incidence of Tuberculosis.³ The vaccine is given routinely in more than 100 countries to newborns as part of the childhood vaccination program.⁴ BCG immunisation coverage varies by country. The estimated BCG coverage for 2022, reported by the World Health Organisation, ranged from 84% in South Africa and 74% in Nigeria to 91% and 100% in India and China, respectively.⁵

The BCG vaccine is administered via intradermal injection into the left deltoid muscle and elicits a local immune response after 6–8 weeks, resulting in swelling, followed by an ulcer that heals, leaving a flat, permanent scar at the injection site.⁶ The BCG scar size seems to correlate with tuberculin skin test (TST) response. In addition, studies indicate that children who develop a scar following BCG vaccination have a 39% (26–49%)

lower mortality rate than those who do not develop a scar.⁷ In one study conducted in southern Nigeria, 96.3% of BCG-vaccinated children had a visible scar, demonstrating a very high prevalence in that setting.⁸ Similarly, a research by Mustafa⁹ in Sudan found 81% prevalence of BCG scar among infants, supporting its utility as an indicator of prior vaccination. Other studies have reported prevalence rates ranging from around 80% to over 90% in infants, though these rates can be influenced by factors such as age at vaccination, vaccination technique, and vaccine strain.^{10,11} Studies conducted in some low-income countries found that children who received BCG vaccination and subsequently developed a scar had a lower incidence of all-cause mortality and fewer hospital admissions than children who did not develop scars following BCG vaccination.^{7,12,13} Failure to form a scar may be due to multiple factors, including lack of immune system maturation, vaccine administration technique, vaccine potency, babies' nutritional status, and other factors.¹⁴⁻¹⁶ The evaluation of the factors influencing BCG scarring following vaccination in Nigeria is a crucial public health concern, as it is an essential indicator of successful BCG vaccination, which is associated with lower child mortality. If these factors are found to be modifiable, they may offer a chance to enhance the protective survival effects of BCG immunisation. This study assessed factors related to the occurrence of scarring following BCG vaccination within a developing nation that bears a significant burden of tuberculosis and child mortality.

Materials and Methods

Study Site

Adamawa State is one of Nigeria's largest states. It is in the country's Northeastern zone. It is bounded by Borno State to the Northwest, Gombe State to the West, Taraba State to the Southwest and the National eastern border by Cameroon. Adamawa State has twenty-one (21) Local Government Areas, which were grouped into three senatorial zones. Yola is situated in the State's central senatorial zone. Modibbo Adama University Teaching Hospital (MAUTH) is situated in Yola Town, Yola South Local Government Area (LGA) of Adamawa State. It is a tertiary health institution which has a bed capacity of 400. It provides primary, secondary and tertiary health care services to inhabitants of Adamawa state, and serves as a referral centre to neighbouring local government areas and States such as Taraba and Borno and part of the Cameroon Republic. The hospital has a public health department that provides routine immunisation services to children in addition to other public

health services. This department has 7 Doctors, 6 nurses and 12 community health extension workers (CHEW). The CHEWs are responsible for administering routine immunisation to children.

Study Design

The study was a cross-sectional descriptive facility-based study and which was conducted at MAUTH Yola over six months, from July to December 2024.

Study Population

The study population were children who had previously received their BCG vaccination and had presented for subsequent vaccines in the National Programme on Immunisation schedule at the immunisation clinic in MAUTH Yola. The children who met the inclusion criteria were recruited for the study.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Children who presented for routine Immunization and have received BCG vaccination.
2. Children for whom consent has been obtained from the parent/caregiver

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Children with a skin lesion on the left forearm.
2. Children on steroids or intravenous immunoglobulin.
3. Children with acute illness.

Sample Size Calculation

The minimum sample size was calculated using this formula

$$n = Z^2 pq / d^2$$

Where:

n= minimum sample size

p= The proportion of the target population estimated to have a particular characteristic (in this case, the prevalence of 81.5% was used as obtained from ABUTH study by Gambo et al¹⁸

q= 1- p, d= Tolerable margin of error = 0.05

Z= standard normal deviate, usually set at 1.96, which corresponds to 95% confidence interval.

p = 81.5%, p = 81.5/100= 0.815, q= 1-0.815= 0.185

n= (1.96)² x 0.815 x 0.185/0.05²

n= 232

Twenty per cent of 232 will be added for non-response; that is, 46 + 232 = 278.

Sampling Technique

All children who were brought to the immunisation clinic by their caregivers and met the enrolment criteria were consecutively included in the study after obtaining informed consent.

Study Instrument

The data was collected using a questionnaire which had undergone face and content validation by three

(3) independent research experts in the field of public health, ensuring its clarity, relevance and appropriateness for the study. The questionnaire comprises three sections. Section A contains information about sociodemographic characteristics. Information on the child's age, sex and place of birth was obtained. Maternal characteristics such as maternal age, education and employment status were also collected. Section B assessed the presence of BCG scar in the child, while Section C comprises 9-item questions assessing factors related to scar formation (age at vaccination, antenatal care, gestational age at birth, history of medications during BCG vaccination and family history of tuberculosis)

Weight Measurement

The weight was measured using a standard Bassinet scale (Salter Tm mode 180, England) with a sensitivity of 0.05kg for infants and children under 2 years of age. Before placing the patient on the weighing scale, the scale was readjusted to zero each time for a new reading by the investigator and his trained assistant. All clothing, including the diaper, was removed to ensure an accurate reading on the weighing scale.

Length Measurement

The supine length was measured with the child on the back and firmly immobilised with the aid of an assistant on a firm surface and the length was read off with a non-elastic measuring tape.

Nutritional Status Determination

The length and weight were converted to z-scores using the National Health Statistics (NHS) weight for height z-score table by WHO to classify the subjects for nutritional status¹⁹. Children with weight for height z-scores of <-2SD were classified wasted, while those with z-scores \geq -2SD were classified as normal.

BCG Scar Identification

The left upper arm around the deltoid was examined by the researcher for the presence or absence of a BCG scar and the findings were documented.

Data Analysis

The data collected was recorded in a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and transferred to SPSS version 22 for analysis. Univariate analyses were conducted for all variables to assess their distributions. Continuous variables were summarised using means, median and standard deviations, while categorical variables were summarised using proportions. The chi-square test was used to assess associations between categorical variables, with a p-value <0.05 considered statistically significant.

Ethics/Consent Consideration

Ethical approvals were obtained from the Health Research and Ethics Committee of MAUTH Yola. The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki of the World Medical Association. Informed written consent (Consent form) was obtained from the parents or caregivers after explaining the nature of the study to them.

Results

General characteristics of the study population.

A total of 277 children were enrolled in the study over six months. Males were 146(52.7%) and females were 131 (47.3%), giving a male-to-female ratio of 1.1:1. The age range of the study population was two (2) months to 24 months, with a median age of 6 months. One hundred and sixty (57.8%) were aged less than six months, while 242 (87.4%) were delivered in a health facility and 35 (12.6%) were delivered at home. One hundred and sixty-three were exclusively breastfed and 14 (5.1%) were wasted (weight for height z scores of < -2SD). Majority of the mothers were between 25-34 (139- 50.2%) age group. Only four (1.4%) had no form of formal education and 45 (16.2%) were also employed. (Table 1)

Prevalence of BCG scar among the study population

Of the 277 children enrolled in the study, 259 had a BCG scar following vaccination, giving a BCG scar prevalence of 93.5%. There was no scar in 18 study children, yielding a BCG scar failure prevalence of 6.5% (Table 2).

Factors related to BCG scar formation

The general characteristics variables analysed were age, gestational age, and history of fever. ANC attendance during pregnancy, co-administration of BCG vaccine with other vaccines, etc. A statistically significant association was observed between children receiving drugs (e.g., antibiotics or analgesics) during BCG vaccination and BCG scar formation. ($X^2 = 6.149$ p=0.013). (Table 3).

Discussion

The study population comprised predominantly children aged six months and below (57.8%) and the male gender (52.7%). This general characteristic compares well with similar studies done in Benin⁸ where 54.7% of their study population were males. In this study, 75.1% of the children received their BCG vaccination within the first week of life. This is similar to what was reported by Atimati et al⁸ in Benin, in which about 72% of children in their study were vaccinated in the first week of life.

Table 1: Characteristics of the study participants (n = 277).

Variable	Frequency	%
Age group (months)		
1-6	160	57.8
7-11	74	26.7
≥12	43	15.5
Median age (IQR)	6months (2-9)	
Age at vaccination (days)		
0-7	208	75.1
8-28	48	17.3
≥28	21	7.6
Place of birth		
Home	35	12.6
Hospital	242	87.4
Exclusive breastfeeding		
No	114	41.2
Yes	163	58.8
Nutritional status		
Normal	263	94.9
Wasted	14	5.1
Mother's age group		
15-24	92	33.2
25-34	139	50.2
≥35	46	16.6
Mean mother's age ± SD	27.9 ± 6.2	
Religion of Parents		
Christianity	76	27.4
Islam	201	72.6
Mother's Educational Status		
No formal education	4	1.4
Formal education	273	98.6
Mother's occupation		
Employed	45	16.2
Not employed	232	83.8

Table 2: Prevalence of the study population

	BCG Scar	
	Frequency n (277)	Percentage (%)
Presence of BCG		
Yes	259	93.5
No	18	6.5

However, this contrasts with Katarina et al²⁰ A study in Guinea-Bissau showed that just 25% of children were vaccinated in the first week of life. This difference could be due to the restrictive vial-opening policy implemented to minimise BCG vaccine wastage in Guinea-Bissau²¹ This practice delays administering the BCG vaccine at birth and within the first week of life.

The prevalence of BCG scar formation in this study is 93.5%. This study compares well with the prevalence of 94% by Atimati *et al* at Benin, Nigeria⁸, 99% by both Santiago *et al* in Peru²² and Castro *et al* in Mozambique²³. Other similar studies include a prevalence of 91% by Jensen *et al* in Denmark¹⁰ and 89% in Sri Lanka²⁴. However, lower rates of 57% was reported by Mustapha *et al* in Maiduguri, Nigeria²⁵ and 47% in Spain by Villanueva²⁶. This difference in prevalence observed in Mustapha's work might be due to differences in the age groups studied. Mustapha *et al* study population were children aged 3 – 59months as opposed to 1.5 months – 24months in our study, with children between the ages of 1.5months – 6months forming the majority (57.8.7%) of our study population. The reduced prevalence of visible BCG scars observed among older children may partly be explained by the gradual fading of the vaccination scar over time. A study conducted in India reported substantial scar disappearance over time, with up to 52% of scars fading within 21 months after vaccination in young children, and continued reduction in scar visibility across older age groups.²⁷

Although several factors have been assessed in relation to BCG scar formation, age of child, gender and nutritional status were not found to be significantly associated with BCG scarring. This finding is comparable to observations reported in Nigeria⁸ and Peru²² which did not find a significant association between scar formation and age, gender and nutritional status.

Table 3: Factors associated with BCG Scar formation (n = 277).

Variable	BCG Scar Absent (n= 18) f (%)	Present (n =259) f (%)	χ^2	p-value
Age group (months)				
1.5-6	8 (5.0)	152 (95.0)	2.572 ⁺	0.337
7-11	5 (6.8)	69 (93.2)		
≥12	5 (11.6)	38 (88.4)		
Gender				
Female	7 (5.3)	124 (94.7)	0.545	0.460
Male	11 (7.5)	135 (92.5)		
Place of birth				
Home	4 (11.4)	31 (88.6)	1.603 ⁺	0.260
Hospital	14 (5.8)	228 (94.2)		
Exclusive Breastfeeding				
No	4 (3.5)	110 (96.5)	2.849	0.091
Yes	14 (8.6)	149 (91.4)		
Mother's age group (years)				
15-24	8 (8.7)	84 (91.3)	1.207	0.547
25-34	8 (5.8)	131 (94.2)		
≥35	2 (4.3)	44 (95.7)		
Mother's Educational status				
Formal education	18 (6.6)	255 (93.4)	0.282 ⁺	1.000
No formal education	0 (0.0)	4 (100.0)		
Mother's occupation				
Employed	3 (6.7)	42 (93.3)	0.003 ⁺	1.000
Not employed	15 (6.5)	217 (93.5)		
Age at vaccination (days)				
0-7	14 (6.7)	194 (93.3)	0.137	0.934
8-28	3 (6.3)	45 (93.8)		
≥28	1 (4.8)	20 (95.2)		
Gestational age of pregnancy				
Preterm	1 (3.1)	31 (96.9)	0.678 ⁺	0.704
Term	17 (6.9)	228 (93.1)		
Fever during the BCG vaccination				
No	16 (7.0)	211 (93.0)	0.627 ⁺	0.750
Yes	2 (4.0)	48 (96.0)		
Family history of TB				
No	18 (6.6)	256 (93.4)	0.211 ⁺	1.000
Yes	0 (0.0)	3 (100.0)		
Child on drugs during BCG vaccine.				
No	16 (9.4)	154 (90.6)	6.149	0.013*
Yes	2 (1.9)	105 (98.1)		
ANC				
No	2 (20.0)	8 (80.0)	3.113 ⁺	0.132
Yes	16 (6.0)	251 (94.0)		
OPV co-administered				
No	5 (6.8)	69 (93.2)	0.011 ⁺	1.000
Yes	13 (6.4)	190 (93.6)		
Nutritional status				
Normal	16 (6.1)	247 (93.9)	1.472 ⁺	0.228
Wasted	2 (14.3)	12 (85.7)		

*Corrected Chi-Square Test, *Statistically significant

There was, however, a significant association between the history of drug administration (analgesics or antibiotics) during BCG administration and BCG scar formation in the study population. Although one would expect that these drugs could interfere with the normal mechanism of scar formation or prevent the appropriate body's response to the vaccines, as reported by Primula et

al²⁸ where they found use of prophylactic paracetamol at the time of vaccination interferes with the antibody response to vaccines in a controlled trial. The interpretation of this finding will require further investigations, particularly because BCG scarring following vaccination may be influenced by multiple factors. Our research limitations concern details of specific antibiotics and analgesics, duration, and the indications for prescription.

We found no significant association between maternal age, maternal education, maternal religion and BCG scarring. This outcome is in agreement with Marban -Castro et al in Mozambique²³, where they found no statistical association between BCG scarring and maternal age, education or religion. These findings could be due to social factors that do not directly affect the formation of scars following BCG vaccination.

This study did not observe a significant relationship between gestational age and BCG scarring. This agrees with Cebeci et al²⁹ who found no significant difference in scar formation between term and preterm infants. In contrast, Atimati et al⁸ reported a significant association between gestational age and BCG scarring. One will generally expect a relationship between gestational age and BCG scarring since preterm babies, due to immunologic immaturity, may not be able to mount enough immune response following BCG vaccination that would lead to scar formation. However, evidence from other studies indicates that preterm infants respond to BCG vaccination as effectively as full-term infants.^{30,31} These differences highlight the need for further investigation.

Conclusion

This study demonstrated a high prevalence of BCG scar formation following vaccination in children, and administering the BCG vaccine while children are on other medications (analgesics or antibiotics) was significantly associated with BCG scarring. We therefore recommend prospective studies to clarify the association between medication use and BCG scarring.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest regarding this study.

Limitation: One limitation of this study is the inability to examine the impact of different BCG strains on scar formation, as only one strain is used in the study setting as part of the national immunisation program. However, this uniformity

eliminates vaccine-related variability, allowing for a better assessment of other factors

Authors' contributions: All the authors have approved the manuscript and agree to its submission. SGB and WSB conceived and designed the study protocol. SGB and WSB collected the data and supervised the work. SGB, OFM and HA analysed and interpreted the data. SGB, OFM and WSB drafted the manuscript. OFM and HA critically revised the manuscript for its scholarly content.

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References

1. Roy A, Eisenhut M, Harris R, Rodrigues L, Sridhar S, Habermann S, *et al.* Effect of BCG vaccination against Mycobacterium tuberculosis infection in children: Systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMJ*. 2014 Aug;349. doi:10.1136/bmj.g4643 PubMed PMID: 25097193.
2. World Health Organisation. Global tuberculosis report 2025. Geneva; 2025. Report.
3. Fine PEM, Carneiro IAM, Milstien JB, Clements CJ. Issues relating to the use of BCG in immunisation programmes. World Health Organisation, Geneva [Internet]. Geneva; 1999 [cited 2026 Jan 14]. Report. Available from: www.who.int/gpv-documents/
4. Zwerling A, Behr MA, Verma A, Brewer TF, Menzies D, Pai M. The BCG world atlas: A database of global BCG vaccination policies and practices. *PLoS Med*. 2011 Mar;8(3). doi:10.1371/journal.pmed.1001012 PubMed PMID: 21445325.
5. World Health Organisation. Nigeria: WHO and UNICEF estimates of immunisation coverage [Internet]. Geneva; 2022 [cited 2026 Jan 14]. Available from: <https://data.unicef.org/topic/child-health/immunization/>
6. Sivaraman N, Sivayogan S, Jegatheesan J, Affiliations G. BCG vaccination and development of a scar. *Ceylon Med J* [Internet]. 1990 Jun;35(2):75-82. Available

- from:
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/2379267/>
7. Benn CS, Roth A, Garly ML, Fisker AB, Schartz-Buchholzer F, Timmermann A, *et al.* BCG scarring and improved child survival: a combined analysis of studies of BCG scarring. *Journal of Internal Medicine*. Blackwell Publishing Ltd; 2020. p. 614–24. doi:10.1111/joim.13084 PubMed PMID: 32301189.
 8. Atimati AO, Osarogiagbon OW. Prevalence of BCG scar among BCG-vaccinated children in a southern Nigeria tertiary hospital. *Niger J Paed*. 2014;41(3):229–33. doi:10.4314/njp.v41i3.15
 9. Mustafa SA. Prevalence of BCG scar among vaccinated children and its correlation with the Mantoux skin test in the Omdawanban area, Sudan. *Tuberculosis [Internet]*. 2025 Mar;151. Available from: <https://doi.org/>
 10. Jensen TM, Jensen SK, Birk NM, Rieckmann A, Hoffmann T, Benn CS, *et al.* Determinants of Bacille Calmette-Guérin scarification in Danish children. *Heliyon*. 2021 Jan;7(1). doi:10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e05757
 11. Dhanawade S, Kumbhar S, Gore A, Patil V. Scar formation and tuberculin conversion following BCG vaccination in infants: A prospective cohort study. *J Family Med Prim Care*. 2015;4(3):384. doi:10.4103/2249-4863.161327
 12. Garly ML, Martins C, Balé C, Baldé M, Hedegaard K, Gustafson P, *et al.* Vaccine BCG scar and positive tuberculin reaction associated with reduced child mortality in West Africa: A non-specific beneficial effect of BCG? *Vaccine*. 2003 Jun;21(21–22):2782–90.
 13. Roth A, Sodemann M, Jensen H, Poulsen A, Gustafson P, Weise C, *et al.* Tuberculin reaction, BCG scar, and lower female mortality. *Epidemiology*. 2006 Sep;17(5):562–8. doi:10.1097/01.ede.0000231546.14749.ab PubMed PMID: 16878042.
 14. Elliott AM, Mawa PA, Webb EL, Nampijja M, Lyadda N, Bukusuba J, *et al.* Effects of maternal and infant co-infections and of maternal immunisation on the infant's response to BCG and tetanus immunisation. *Vaccine*. 2010 Dec 16;29(2):247–55. doi:10.1016/j.vaccine.2010.10.047 PubMed PMID: 21040693.
 15. Moliva J, Turner J, Torrelles JB. Immune responses to bacillus Calmette-Guérin vaccination: Why do they fail to protect against mycobacterium tuberculosis? *Front Immunol*. 2017 Apr;8(407). doi:10.3389/fimmu.2017.00407 PubMed PMID: 28424703.
 16. Roth A, Sodemann M, Jensen H, Poulsen A, Gustafson P, Gomes J, *et al.* Vaccination technique, PPD reaction and BCG scarring in a cohort of children born in Guinea-Bissau 2000–2002. *Vaccine*. 2005 Jun;23(30):3991–8.
 17. Lwanga SK, Lameshow S. Sample Size Determination in Health Studies. In. Geneva; 1991.
 18. Gambo MJ, Lawan UM, Ahmad HR, Ogala WN. Assessment of tuberculin reactivity of BCG-vaccinated infants in Zaria, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Basic and Clinical Sciences*. 2014 Jul 1;11(2):104–9. doi:10.4103/0331-8540.140360
 19. World Health Organization. WHO [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2026 Jan 7]. Child Growth Standard. Available from: <https://www.who.int/childgrowth>
 20. Funch KM, Thyssen SM, Rodrigues A, Martins CL, Aaby P, Benn CS, *et al.* Determinants of BCG scarification among children in rural Guinea-Bissau: A prospective cohort study. *Hum Vaccin Immunother*. 2018 Oct 3;14(10):2434–42. doi:10.1080/21645515.2017.1421879 PubMed PMID: 29293396.
 21. Thyssen SM, Byberg S, Pedersen M, Rodrigues A, Ravn H, Martins C, *et al.* BCG coverage and barriers to BCG vaccination in Guinea-Bissau: An observational study. *BMC Public Health*. 2014 Oct 4;14(1). doi:10.1186/1471-2458-14-1037 PubMed PMID: 25282475.
 22. Santiago EM, Lawson E, Gillenwater K, Kalangi S, Lescano AG, Du Quella G, *et al.* A prospective study of bacillus Calmette-Guérin scar formation and tuberculin skin test reactivity in infants in Lima, Peru. *Pediatrics*. 2003;112(4). doi:10.1542/peds.112.4.e298 PubMed PMID: 14523215.
 23. Marbán-Castro E, Sacoor C, Nhacolo A, Augusto O, Jamisse E, López-Varela E, *et al.* BCG vaccination in southern rural Mozambique: An overview of coverage and

- its determinants based on data from the demographic and health surveillance system in the district of Manhiça. *BMC Pediatr.* 2018 Feb 13;18(1). doi:10.1186/s12887-018-1003-4 PubMed PMID: 29439702.
24. Srisaravanapavanathan N, Dissanayake NN, Sarathchandra J. BCG vaccination scars of children under five years in a tertiary care hospital. *Sri Lanka Journal of Child Health.* 2008. Report.
25. Mustapha MG, Garba MA, Rabasa AI, Farouk AG. Prevalence of BCG Scar Formation Among BCG Vaccinated Apparently Healthy U-5 Children and its Correlation with Mantoux Skin Test Induration in Maiduguri, Nigeria. *Niger Med J.* 2008;49(4):84-7.
26. Villanueva P, Crawford NW, Croda MG, Collopy S, Jardim BA, de Almeida Pinto Jardim T, *et al.* Factors influencing scar formation following Bacille Calmette-Guérin (BCG) vaccination. *Heliyon.* 2023 Apr 1;9(4). doi:10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e15241
27. National Tuberculosis Institute. Tuberculin testing in a partly BCG vaccinated population. *an Journal of TB.* 1992;(39):149-58.
28. Prymula R, Siegrist CA, Chlibek R, Zemlickova H, Vackova M, Smetana J, *et al.* Effect of prophylactic paracetamol administration at time of vaccination on febrile reactions and antibody responses in children: two open-label, randomised controlled trials. *The Lancet.* 2009;374(9698):1339-50. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(09)61208-3 PubMed PMID: 19837254.
29. Cebeci SO, Kavuncuoglu S, Turel O, Aldemir EY, Kazanci SY. Scar formation and tuberculin skin test response after bacillus Calmette-Guerin vaccination: Does prematurity or low birth weight have an impact? *Iran J Pediatr.* 2017 Apr 1;27(2). doi:10.5812/ijp.4932
30. Thayyil-Sudhan S, Kumar A, Singh M, Paul VK, Deorari AK. Safety and effectiveness of BCG vaccination in preterm babies. *Arch Dis Child Fetal Neonatal Ed.* 1999;81:64-9.
31. Negrete-Esqueda L, Vargas-Origel A. Response to Bacillus Calmette-Guérin vaccine in full-term and preterm infants. *Am J Perinatol.* 2007 ;24(3):183-9. doi:10.1055/s-2007-970080 PubMed PMID: 17372860.